

Classroom Management: Attitude and Belief of Secondary School Teachers

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ABSTRACT : Classroom management is considered as an important and prevalent problem of teachers. Classroom management behaviour of teachers, in general, depends upon the belief and attitude of teachers towards classroom management. The purpose of the study was to investigate the attitude and belief towards classroom management of teachers of secondary schools in Howrah District of West Bengal. Data were collected from the 122 teachers of different categories, viz., Locality of school (urban and rural), Sex (male and female), and Academic discipline (arts and science) by applying a psychometric instrument, Behaviour and Instruction Management Scale (BIMS) developed by Martin and Sass, 2010. Results showed that female teachers were significantly more controlling towards the classroom management than the male teachers. But, with respect to both the Locality and Academic discipline, no significant difference was observed between the respective teacher groups.

Keywords : Behaviour management, Instruction management, Classroom Management, Attitude and Belief

Introduction

Development of appropriate environment for better classroom teaching is the most significant aspect of the contemporary formal system of education. Only the sociable and favourable environment in the classroom may create the desired level of learning environment to motivate and activate the learners to lend hands with the

co-learners to maintain the academic discipline. Teachers' responsibility as a leader in the classroom is to manage instruction and behaviour in the classroom so that a good climate can exist and at the end the target of learning fulfils. Classroom teachers' managerial ability, their awareness about the classroom management models and strategies, their belief regarding

classroom management and above all, adoption and application of those models and strategies in the classrooms may help them in creating such a favourable situation in the classroom. Wang, Haertel and Walberg (1993) demonstrated that among 228 variables (which come under 30 categories within six theoretical constructs), classroom management as a category under theoretical construct of classroom practices had the largest effect on student achievement. This can lead to the sense that students can not learn in a disordered, inadequately managed classroom.

Olson and Maio (2003) suggest that attitudes express people's beliefs and attitudes can be evoked by beliefs. They also conclude that individuals behave in ways that are consistent with their attitudes or in other words, attitudes influence action. Classroom management behaviour or practice of teachers, in general, depends upon the belief and attitude of teachers towards classroom management. Glickman and Tamashiro (1980) categorize the attitude of teachers in the classroom while they are managing the classroom into three categories- non interventionist, interactionalist and interventionist.

Interventionist's belief focuses on high controlling behaviour by the teacher as it thinks that a child is conditioned by his or her environment and the teacher needs to intervene and become the controller of the environment for the cause of development of the child. Non-interventionists suggest that students should be allowed to exercise significant authority and power in the classroom and that teacher should be less involved in adjusting student behaviours (Hoang, 2009). Interactionalists intend that students and teachers should share responsibility

for maintaining order in the classroom and manage it well and both the teachers and students are accountable for well management of the classroom (Martin, Yin & Baldwin, 1998). Martin and Baldwin (1992) believe that teachers' approach towards managing the classrooms differ due to their beliefs regarding the nature of behaviours (appropriate and inappropriate) and the way to control the behaviour.

In a study of Relationships between Pre-service Teachers' Self-Efficacy, Task Analysis and Classroom Management Beliefs, Henson (2001) tried to examine the multivariate relationships between teacher efficacy and task analysis variables of predictors of classroom management beliefs about control. Data analysis indicated that more efficacious student teachers were less interventionist regarding instructional and people management beliefs. Task analysis was unrelated to management beliefs. However, pre-service teachers exhibited a clear dichotomy regarding their locus of control for task analysis elements. The task analysis suggested differential locus of control for elements that helped teaching (attributed to the self) and elements that hindered teaching (attributed to external constraints).

Study by Martin et al. (2006) revealed significant differences between novice teachers and their more experienced counterparts on both the Instructional Management (IM) and the People Management (PM) sub-scale of Attitude and Belief on Classroom Control (ABCC) Inventory. But in opposite direction, experienced teachers, those with six or more years' experience, scored more controlling on the IM sub-scale but less controlling on the PM sub-scale. The inexperienced teachers scored significantly less interventionist on the IM

dimension. No significant differences regarding gender were ascertained on the PM Sub-scale, though the IM Sub-scale yielded significance regarding gender with female teachers scoring more controlling than males.

Classroom Management is an umbrella term that encompasses teacher efforts to oversee the activities of the classroom including student behaviour, student interactions and learning. It is operationalized as behavioural tendencies that teachers utilize to conduct daily instructional activities. These tendencies reflect the teacher's discipline, communication, and instructional styles (Martin and Sass, 2010).

An attitude is a hypothetical construct that represents an individual's degree of like or dislike for an item. Attitudes are generally positive or negative views of a person, place, thing, or event - this is often referred to as the attitude object. People can also be conflicted or ambivalent toward an object, meaning that they simultaneously possess both positive and negative attitudes toward the item in question. Belief is the psychological state in which an individual holds a proposition or premise to be true. In the field of classroom management studies, researchers use the composite parameter of attitude and belief for their research studies. Behaviour management (BM) is similar to, but different, from discipline in that it includes pre-planned efforts to avert misbehaviour as well as the teacher's response to it. Instructional management (IM) deals with teachers' instructional techniques and methodologies and includes features such as supervising seatwork and organizing daily routines as well as the teacher's use of lecture and student practice, interactive, participatory approaches to instruction.

Martin and Sass (2010) had developed a new scale called Behaviour and Instruction Management Scale (BIMS) which has two independent construct – Behaviour Management (BM) and Instruction Management (IM). The BIMS is psychometrically sounder instrument designed to measure the aspects of teachers' beliefs towards managing behaviour and instruction. In this context, the present study deals with attitude and belief towards classroom management of teachers of West Bengal.

Objective of the study

- i. To compare the attitude and belief towards the classroom management of teachers under different categories, viz., Locality of school, Gender and Academic discipline;
- ii. To know the status of attitude and beliefs of teachers towards the classroom management

The Hypotheses

- oH1: There is no significant difference between the teachers of urban and rural schools on the criteria of attitude and belief towards behaviour management.
- oH2: There is no significant difference between the teachers of urban and rural schools on the criteria of attitude and belief towards instruction management.
- oH3: There is no significant difference between the male and female teachers on the criteria of attitude and belief towards behaviour management.
- oH4: There is no significant difference between the male and female teachers on the criteria of attitude and belief towards instruction management.

oH5: There is no significant difference between the teachers of arts discipline and the science discipline on the criteria of the attitude and belief towards behaviour management.

oH6: There is no significant difference between the teachers of arts discipline and the science discipline on the criteria of the attitude and belief towards instruction management.

oH7: There are no significant differences among the urban male, urban female, rural male and rural female teachers on the criteria of attitude and belief towards behaviour management.

oH8: There are no significant differences among the urban male, urban female, rural male and rural female teachers on the criteria of attitude and belief towards instruction management.

Table 1. Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Discipline of Subject * Sex * Locality of School	122	100.0%	0	0%	122	100.0%

Table 2. Discipline of Subject * Sex * Locality of School Cross Tabulation

Count					
Locality of School	Discipline of Subject	Sex			
		Male	Female	Total	
Urban	Arts	13	23	36	
	Science	13	8	21	
	Total	26	31	57	
Rural	Arts	19	20	39	
	Science	15	11	26	
	Total	34	31	65	

oH1 and oH2

Table 3. Group Statistics * Urban and Rural

	Locality of School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
BM	urban	57	4.6199	.62162	.08234
	rural	65	4.7308	.49340	.06120
IM	urban	57	3.0278	.48267	.06393
	rural	65	2.9449	.37652	.04670

Methodology

Sample: The sample was selected

purposively from the different schools of Howrah district. The teachers were from boys', girls and co-ed schools under urban (municipality) and rural (Panchayat) areas. All the schools were aided by Government of West Bengal and academically controlled by West Bengal Board of Secondary Education and West Bengal

Table 4. Independent Samples Test _ urban vs rural

	t-test for Equality of Means			
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
BM	-1.097**	120	.275	-.11089
IM	1.064**	120	.289	.08291

** Not significant at 0.05 level

oH3 and oH4

Table 5. Group Statistics _ Male & Female

	Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
BM	male	60	4.5375	.53578	.06917
	female	62	4.8159	.54763	.06955
IM	male	60	2.9611	.50782	.06556
	female	62	3.0054	.34005	.04319

Table 6. - Independent Samples Test _ Male vs Female

	t-test for Equality of Means			
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
BM	-2.837*	120	.005	-.27836
IM	-.567**	120	.571	-.04427

(* Significant at 0.05 level of significance; ** Not significant at 0.05 level.)

Council for Higher Secondary Education (for H.S. sections). The sample frames are shown below in Tables 1 and 2:

Tools: To collect data from the sampled teachers regarding their attitude and belief towards their respective classroom management, the Behaviour and Instruction Management scale (BIMS), developed by Martin and Sass, 2010, was administered which

was a psychometrically sounder scale. Since the BIMS (2010) had been published in 'Teaching and Teacher Education', an International Journal of Research and Studies, published by Elsevier, and presently copyright is with the publisher, to use the scale, permission was seek from the authors and it was granted through email. This scale measures the attitude and belief of teachers how much they are controlling. BIMS has two dimensions - (i) behaviour management and (ii) instruction management. It has 24 items, among which 12 items were on behaviour management dimension and 12 were on instruction management dimension. Each item has six categories of responses which are - strongly agree, agree, slightly agree, slightly disagree, disagree, and

strongly disagree and '6', '5', '4', '3', '2', '1' are the respective scores to be awarded for the responses. Some items are negative and the scoring is done on reversed order.

Scoring procedure

In accordance with the response to the category of each item, scores were given ranging from '6' to '1'. Mean score on each subscale i.e. behaviour management and instruction

oH5 and oH6

Table 7. Group Statistics _ Arts teachers & Science teachers

	Discipline of Subject	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
BM	arts	75	4.6711	.49583	.05725
	science	47	4.6915	.64921	.09470
IM	arts	75	3.0056	.38685	.04467
	science	47	2.9486	.49256	.07185

Table 8. Independent Samples Test _ Arts teacher vs Science teachers

	t-test for Equality of Means			
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
BM	-.196**	120	.845	-.02038
IM	.711**	120	.478	.05697

(** Not significant at 0.05 level.)

management was calculated for every teacher. The scoring was done in consultation with the principal author of BIMS, Prof. N. K. Martin.

Results

The collected data were been analyzed through SPSS17.0 version and the significance of t values were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

The analyses in Table 4 show that urban teachers and rural teachers do not differ significantly in their attitude and belief towards behaviour management (BM) and instruction management (IM) sub-scales of BIMS as the t values are not significant and p values are .275 and .289 ($p > 0.05$) respectively.

The analysis in Table 6 shows that t value (2.837) in BM sub-scale is significant ($p < 0.05$) and in IM sub-scale, t value (0.567) is not

significant ($p > 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis H_3 is rejected and H_4 not rejected. That means male and female teachers are significantly different from each other in their attitude and belief regarding behaviour management but not significantly different in instruction management.

Analysis in Table 8 shows that in both the cases like BM and IM, the calculated t values (in BM 0.196 and IM 0.711) are not significant ($p > 0.05$). Hence the hypothesis H_5 and H_6 are not rejected. So it can be said that the teachers of

Arts discipline and the teachers of Science discipline do not differ significantly in their attitude and belief towards behaviour management and instruction management.

Analysis in Table 10 show F value is significant ($F_{3,118} = 3.745$, $p < 0.05$) in BM sub-scale. So, H_7 is rejected and it can be said that the groups are significantly different from each other in BM sub-scale. In case of IM sub-scale, the calculated $F_{3,118}$ value is 1.791 and $p > 0.05$, so F is not significant, thus H_8 not rejected. So it can be inferred that there are significant differences among the groups of teachers in their attitude and beliefs regarding instruction management. Further analyses had been done to find out which groups were different significantly from others in the attitude and belief towards behaviour management by t test and results are presented in the table 11.

Testing of H_0 and H_1

Table 9. Group Statistics *Locality _ Gender

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
BM	urban male	26	4.3974	.60796	.11923
	urban female	31	4.8065	.57831	.10387
	rural male	34	4.6446	.45380	.07783
	rural female	31	4.8253	.52456	.09421
IM	urban male	26	3.0962	.61810	.12122
	urban female	31	2.9704	.33023	.05931
	rural male	34	2.8578	.38245	.06559
	rural female	31	3.0403	.35150	.06313

Table 10. ANOVA - Locality _Gender

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
BM	Between Groups	3.268	3	1.089	3.745*	.013
	Within Groups	34.324	118	.291		
	Total	37.593	121			
IM	Between Groups	.972	3	.324	1.791**	.153
	Within Groups	21.356	118	.181		
	Total	22.328	121			

(* Significant at 0.05 level of significance; ** Not significant at 0.05 level of significance.)

Table 11. Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means			
		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Total BM	Urban male vs Urban female	-2.598*	55	.012	-4.90819
	Rural male vs Rural female	-1.488**	63	.142	-2.16793
	Urban male vs Rural male	-1.804**	58	.076	-2.96606
	Urban female vs Rural female	-.134**	60	.894	-0.22581

* Significant at 0.05 level of significance; ** Not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Analyses show that the t value calculated for the group urban male and urban female is 2.598 which is significant ($p < 0.05$) at 0.05 level. Other groups had no significant t values. So, it can be concluded that only urban male teachers possess significantly different attitude and beliefs in behaviour management from urban female teachers. Other groups possessed no significantly different attitude and beliefs towards behaviour management.

Discussions

It has been found from the study that teachers of rural area are more controlling than teachers of urban area in behaviour management but that is reversed in case of instruction management; in both the cases the differences in attitude are not significantly more controlling.

But female teachers possess significantly more interventionist attitude and belief towards behaviour management than male teachers. In case of instruction management female teachers are found

more (not significantly) controlling than the male teachers.

The teachers belong to science discipline possess more controlling attitude and belief towards behaviour management but teachers of arts discipline are more controlling than the teachers of science discipline in instruction management; but in no case the attitudes are significantly more controlling.

Interestingly, it is further found that urban female teachers possess significantly more interventionist attitude and belief towards behaviour management than the urban male teachers.

Classroom management is considered as important and widespread problems of teachers. Beliefs and attitude regarding appropriate nature of behaviour determine teachers' behaviour how to manage behaviour and instruction so that classroom can be managed and learning environment can be restored. The purpose of this study was to investigate the attitude and belief towards classroom management of teachers of secondary schools. Results show that female teachers are found significantly more controlling than male teachers but in other categories like locality of school (urban and rural) and academic discipline (arts and science) no significant differences were found. It implies that some factors are there with respect to gender which determines the attitude and belief toward classroom management.

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